

MODELLING OF THE ANISOTROPIC DAMAGE OF UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITE MATERIALS UNDER STATIC AND FATIGUE LOADING

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ABSTRACT

Starting from the present understanding of the directional initiation and growth of microcracks in unidirectional fiber reinforced plastics, an anisotropic damage model of unidirectional composite materials under static and fatigue loading has been developed within the framework of phenomenological thermodynamics of continua with internal variables. As an application of the general model, the structural damage analysis of three-points bending fatigue tests has been performed with taking account of the shear stress effects.

INTRODUCTION

The growing use of composite materials in advanced technological constructions calls for designs that are competitive and economical. Most of fiber reinforced composite structures are made of laminates which consist of uniaxially reinforced laminae (unidirectional composites). Given the very large variety of laminates, it is a sound approach to attempt to determine the mechanical response of laminates to a given loading history from understanding the mechanical behaviour of elementary constituents, which are lamina and interface. The present work is concerned with the modelling of the anisotropic damaged mechanical behaviour of unidirectional composites under static and fatigue loading.

The model will be developed within the framework of phenomenological thermodynamics of continua with internal variables and composed of three parts:

- a. Definition of damage variables characterizing statistically and macroscopically the microstructural damage state of the material;
- b. Description of the mechanical behaviour of the damaged material;
- c. Formulation of the evolution equations for the damage state variables under a given loading history.

As an application of this general model, the bending problem will be investigated taking into account the shear stress effects.

DAMAGE VARIABLES

The phenomenological description of damage is based on the introduction of damage internal variables representing, on a global and macroscopic level, the material degradation of a material resulting from the initiation and propagation of microdefects. In the case of composite materials many damage mechanisms are recognized (fiber breakage, fiber/matrix debonding, matrix cracking,...) and their respective significance essentially depends on the loading history. It should further be emphasized that the compression behaviour may involve more complicated mechanisms and most of our model will be developed for tensile stresses.

The microstructural cracking modes of unidirectional composites have a pronounced directional character and the strongly anisotropic material structure basically controls the anisotropy of damage. Experiments show that the microcracks are essentially initiated and propagated in the directions perpendicular and parallel to the fibers^{1,2,3}. Two fundamental damage modes, the fiber mode and the matrix mode, are therefore distinguished respectively corresponding to these two basic cracking patterns. However, if the fiber mode can be described through a scalar variable D , the matrix mode requires a more complex anisotropic description, involving two bidimensional symmetric second rank tensors \mathbf{d} and ω .

Generalizing the Kachanov effective stress notion^{4,5}, the effective stress tensor $\tilde{\sigma}$ may be expressed as

$$\tilde{\sigma} = \mathbf{M}(D, \mathbf{d}, \omega) : \sigma \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{M}(D, \mathbf{d}, \omega)$ known as damage effect tensor is a linear transformation of the space of all second rank symmetric tensors into itself. We specialize $\mathbf{M}(D, \mathbf{d}, \omega)$ by the following formulation

$$\tilde{\sigma}_{11} = (1-D)^{-1} \sigma_{11} \quad (2a)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\sigma}_{22} & \tilde{\sigma}_{23} \\ \tilde{\sigma}_{32} & \tilde{\sigma}_{33} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 1-d_{22} & d_{23} \\ d_{32} & 1-d_{33} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{22} & \sigma_{23} \\ \sigma_{32} & \sigma_{33} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{22} & \sigma_{23} \\ \sigma_{32} & \sigma_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1-d_{22} & d_{23} \\ d_{32} & 1-d_{33} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \right\} \quad (2b)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\sigma}_{12} \\ \tilde{\sigma}_{13} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\sigma}_{21} \\ \tilde{\sigma}_{31} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1-\omega_{22} & \omega_{23} \\ \omega_{32} & 1-\omega_{33} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{12} \\ \sigma_{13} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2c)$$

the axis x_1 being the fiber direction.

It is easy to verify that the preceding effective stress $\tilde{\sigma}$ is a tensorial invariant function of the usual stress tensor σ and the damage variables D , \mathbf{d} and ω under the orthogonal transformations of the transversely isotropic symmetry group.

DAMAGED ELASTIC BEHAVIOR

For some unidirectional composites (glass/epoxy, graphite/epoxy, etc...) at temperature well below the glass transition temperature, viscous phenomena are negligible and the initial mechanical behaviour can be taken as linearly elastic and transversely isotropic. It is defined by the Gibbs free energy $V(\sigma)$ with five elastic parameters

$$\begin{aligned} V(\sigma) = & \frac{1}{2E_L} \sigma_{11}^2 + \frac{1}{2E_T} (\sigma_{22}^2 + \sigma_{33}^2) - \frac{\nu_L}{E_L} (\sigma_{11}\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{11}\sigma_{33}) - \frac{\nu_T}{E_T} \sigma_{22}\sigma_{33} \\ & + \frac{1}{4G_T} (\sigma_{23}^2 + \sigma_{32}^2) + \frac{1}{4G_L} (\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{21}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2 + \sigma_{31}^2) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

with

$$G_T = \frac{E_T}{2(1+\nu_T)}$$

Cordebois and Sidoroff⁶ have shown that, in order to ensure the symmetry of the damaged elasticity tensors $\tilde{\mathbf{A}} = \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{-1}$ in the case of anisotropic damage, the assumption of strain equivalence proposed for isotropic damage by Lemaître⁷ implies very strong restrictions on the transformation \mathbf{M} . To overcome this inconvenience, they have proposed the hypothesis of elastic energy equivalence according to which the damaged elastic energy is obtained by substituting the effective stress tensor for the usual one in the undamaged elastic energy function. With this hypothesis, the symmetry of the damaged elasticity tensors is automatically satisfied.

For unidirectional composites, the hypothesis of elastic energy equivalence is written as

$$\tilde{V}(\sigma; D, \mathbf{d}, \omega) = V(\tilde{\sigma}) \quad (4)$$

It can be shown⁸ that, if the undamaged elastic energy function V is a scalar invariant function of stress tensor σ under the transformation of the transversely isotropic symmetry group \mathcal{G} and that the effective stress $\tilde{\sigma}$ is a tensorial invariant function of stress tensor σ and the damage variables D , \mathbf{d} and ω under the same transformations of \mathcal{G} , the damaged elastic energy function \tilde{V} obtained through the hypothesis (4) satisfies the following restrictions imposed by the material symmetry

$$\forall Q \in \mathcal{G} : \tilde{V}(Q\sigma Q^T; D, Q\mathbf{d}Q^T, Q\omega Q^T) = \tilde{V}(\sigma; D, \mathbf{d}, \omega) \quad (5)$$

By substituting (2) and (3) into (4), we obtain the anisotropic damaged elastic behaviour of unidirectional composites

$$\boldsymbol{\epsilon} = \frac{\partial \tilde{V}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}; D, \mathbf{d}, \omega)}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \tilde{\mathbf{A}}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}; D, \mathbf{d}, \omega) : \boldsymbol{\sigma} \quad (6)$$

With Voigt's notations, the relation (6) may be expressed as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_1 \\ \epsilon_2 \\ \epsilon_3 \\ \epsilon_4 \\ \epsilon_5 \\ \epsilon_6 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\Lambda}_{11} & \tilde{\Lambda}_{12} & \tilde{\Lambda}_{13} & \tilde{\Lambda}_{14} & 0 & 0 \\ \tilde{\Lambda}_{21} & \tilde{\Lambda}_{22} & \tilde{\Lambda}_{23} & \tilde{\Lambda}_{24} & 0 & 0 \\ \tilde{\Lambda}_{31} & \tilde{\Lambda}_{32} & \tilde{\Lambda}_{33} & \tilde{\Lambda}_{34} & 0 & 0 \\ \tilde{\Lambda}_{41} & \tilde{\Lambda}_{42} & \tilde{\Lambda}_{43} & \tilde{\Lambda}_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \tilde{\Lambda}_{55} & \tilde{\Lambda}_{56} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \tilde{\Lambda}_{65} & \tilde{\Lambda}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \sigma_3 \\ \sigma_4 \\ \sigma_5 \\ \sigma_6 \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

where, for instance,

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\Lambda}_{11} &= \frac{1}{(1-D)^2 E_L}, & \tilde{\Lambda}_{12} &= -\frac{(1-d_{33})\nu_L}{(1-D)\Delta d E_L}, & \tilde{\Lambda}_{14} &= \frac{2d_{23}\nu_L}{(1-D)\Delta d E_L} \\ \tilde{\Lambda}_{22} &= \frac{(1-d_{33})^2}{\Delta^2 d E_T} + \frac{d_{23}^2}{4\Delta^2 d G_T}, & \tilde{\Lambda}_{44} &= -\frac{2d_{23}^2(1-\nu_T)}{\Delta^2 d E_T} + \frac{(2-d_{22}-d_{33})^2}{4\Delta^2 d G_T} \\ \tilde{\Lambda}_{55} &= \frac{(1-\omega_{33})^2 + \omega_{23}^2}{\Delta^2 \omega G_L}, & \tilde{\Lambda}_{56} &= -\frac{(2-\omega_{22}-\omega_{33})\omega_{23}}{\Delta^2 \omega G_L} \end{aligned}$$

with $\Delta d = \det(\mathbf{1}-\mathbf{d})$ and $\Delta \omega = \det(\mathbf{1}-\boldsymbol{\omega})$.

It results from (7) that the damaged unidirectional composites are in general monoclinic (the mechanical response is symmetric about the planes transverse to the fibers).

Based on the concept of effective strain associated with the hypothesis of Helmholtz free energy equivalence⁶, we can develop a dual formulation and derive $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}(D, \mathbf{d}, \omega) = \mathbf{A}^{-1}(D, \mathbf{d}, \omega)$.

DAMAGE EVOLUTION EQUATIONS

Brittle Damage

To describe the progression of the anisotropic damage of unidirectional composites, we consider the Gibbs free energy in the following form

$$\tilde{V}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}; D, \mathbf{d}, \omega, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3) = V(\tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}) - \psi_1(\beta_1) - \psi_2(\beta_2) - \psi_3(\beta_3) \quad (8)$$

where ψ_i ($i=1,2,3$) are degradation energy functions and β_i ($i=1,2,3$) are degradation variables which are analogous to the hardening variables in plasticity⁹.

The Clausius-Duhem inequality takes the form

$$\dot{\tilde{V}}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}; D, \mathbf{d}, \omega, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3) - \boldsymbol{\epsilon} : \dot{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} \geq 0 \quad (9)$$

which gives the energy dissipated by the damage

$$\dot{\phi} = R_k \dot{\alpha}_k \geq 0 \quad (10)$$

where R_k are the thermodynamic forces associated with the damage variables $\boldsymbol{\alpha} = [D, \mathbf{d}, \omega, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3]^T$

$$\underline{R} = [Y, \mathbf{G}, \mathbf{\Omega}, -B_1, -B_2, -B_3]^T$$

$$R_k = \frac{\partial \bar{V}(\alpha_i)}{\partial \alpha_k} \quad (11)$$

Assuming that the anisotropic damage of unidirectional composites is rate-independent, the damage evolution laws will be given by using the general scheme of generalized standard material¹⁰.

Two damage criteria, which respectively describe the fiber mode and the matrix mode, are proposed — fiber mode

$$f_1 = \left[\left(\frac{Y}{B_1} \right)^p + \left(\frac{\sqrt{\text{tr}(\mathbf{\Omega}^2)}}{B_3} \right)^p \right]^{1/p} \leq 1 \quad (12a)$$

— matrix mode

$$f_2 = \left[\frac{\text{tr}(\mathbf{G}^2)}{B_2^2} + 2\xi \frac{\text{tr}(\mathbf{G}\mathbf{\Omega})}{B_2 B_3} + \frac{\text{tr}(\mathbf{\Omega}^2)}{B_3^2} \right]^{1/2} \leq 1 \quad (12b)$$

where p , ξ , $B_1(\beta_1)$, $B_2(\beta_2)$ and $B_3(\beta_3)$ are respectively two material constants and three material functions to be identified.

The brittle damage evolution is defined by the rate equations

$$\dot{\alpha}_i = \lambda_k \frac{\partial f_k}{\partial R_i} \quad (k=1, 2) \quad (13)$$

where the multipliers $\lambda_k \geq 0$ ($k=1, 2$) are determined from the consistency conditions and must satisfy the following relations

$$\begin{cases} \text{if } f_k = 1 : \lambda_k \geq 0, & f_k \leq 0, & \lambda_k \dot{f}_k = 0 \\ \text{if } f_k < 1 : \lambda_k = 0 \\ (k=1, 2; \text{ no summation for } k) \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

Fatigue Damage

It has been observed that the damage development of unidirectional composites under fatigue and static loading is similar except that fatigue at a given stress level causes additional damages to occur as a function of cycles^{11,12,13}. Consequently, in the fatigue damage case, the previous general formulation remains valid provided the preceding damage evolution laws are changed.

The analysis of the structure of the brittle damage kinetic laws (13) and (14) shows that it cannot take into account the continuous damage accumulation under fatigue loading. Following an approach developed by Marigo¹⁴, a unidimensional and a bidimensional fatigue damage kinetic laws have been derived^{15,8}.

APPLICATION TO BENDING FATIGUE

Local Damage Model

The structural damage analysis of three-points bending fatigue tests (Fig.1) has been performed by Sidoroff and Subagio¹⁶. But the shear stress effects, which are of great importance for some circumstances, have not been included

Figure 1

With taking account of the shear stress effects, the damaged elastic laws are given by

$$\sigma(x, y) = E [1 - D(x, y)] \epsilon(x, y) \quad (E = E_L) \quad (15)$$

$$\tau(x, y) = G [1 - \omega(x, y)] \gamma(x, y) \quad (G = G_L, \quad \gamma = 2\epsilon_{12}) \quad (16)$$

The equations governing the fatigue damage evolution have the following form

$$\dot{D} = \begin{cases} r(\epsilon, \dot{\gamma}, D, \omega; \dot{\epsilon}, \dot{\gamma}) & \text{in traction} \\ 0 & \text{in compression} \end{cases} \quad (17a)$$

$$\dot{\omega} = q(\epsilon, \gamma, D, \omega; \dot{\epsilon}, \dot{\gamma}) \quad \text{in traction or compression} \quad (17b)$$

where the functions r and q are homogeneous functions of order one in $\dot{\epsilon}$ and $\dot{\gamma}$.

Structural Analysis

The structural analysis will be made by using Navier-Bernoulli's assumption

$$\epsilon(x, y) = C(x) [y - y_o(x)] \quad (18)$$

where the position of the neutral fiber $y_o(x)$ is defined by

$$y_o(x) = \frac{\int_{-h/2}^{h/2} [1 - D(x, y)] y dy}{\int_{-h/2}^{h/2} [1 - D(x, y)] dy} \quad (19)$$

$M(x)$ being bending moment and $C(x)$ curvature, the bending stiffness $H(x) = M(x)/C(x)$ is given by

$$H(x) = bE \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} [1 - D(x, y)] [y^2 - yy_o(x)] dy \quad (20)$$

From equilibrium, the shear stress $\tau(x, y)$ can be postulated as

$$\tau(x, y) = E \frac{d}{dx} \left\{ \frac{M(x)}{H(x)} \int_y^{h/2} [1 - D(x, y_1)] [y_1 - y_o(x)] dy_1 \right\} \quad (21)$$

The displacement δ then results from Castigliano's theorem

$$\delta = \frac{\partial w}{\partial P} \quad (22)$$

where

$$w = \int_{-l/2}^{l/2} \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \frac{b}{2} [\sigma(x,y)\epsilon(x,y) + \tau(x,y)\gamma(x,y)] dy dx \quad (23)$$

CONCLUSION

Focusing on the essential and specific aspects of the oriented inception and growth of microcracks in unidirectional composites, a general yet simple approach has been proposed for the elastic-brittle and fatigue anisotropic damage of these materials.

Dissymmetrization of the behaviour between tension and compression by distinguishing the active damage (open microcracks) and the passive damage (closed microcracks) will be one possible extension of the present model. One of the main difficulties consists in considering the fact that, despite the one-sided constraint imposed by microcracks on the displacement discontinuity, the stress-strain relation should be continuous.

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